

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice (KAP) Study of Hepatitis B Infection among Medical Students of Udaipur: A Cross-Sectional Study**Chandan Mal Fatehpuria¹, Mahesh Upadhyay², Chandra Prakash Sharma¹, Ashish Jain², Jatin Prajapati³, Shivani Vihan³**¹Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India³PG student, Department of Community Medicine, RNT Medical College, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

Received: 01-10-2024 Revised: 15-11-2024 / Accepted: 21-12-2024

Corresponding author: Dr. Ashish Jain

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Background:** Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection is a major global public health concern, particularly for healthcare workers and medical students due to their frequent exposure to blood and body fluids. Despite the availability of effective vaccines and preventive measures, gaps in awareness and practices persist among future healthcare providers.**Objectives:** To assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) regarding Hepatitis B infection among undergraduate medical students in Udaipur and identify factors influencing preventive behavior.**Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted among 420 undergraduate medical students using a pretested, semi-structured, self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire covered demographic details and KAP-related items. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and correlation analysis to evaluate relationships between knowledge, attitude, and practice scores.**Results:** Out of 420 participants, 59.3% demonstrated good knowledge, 71.2% showed a positive attitude, but only 54.8% were fully vaccinated. Awareness regarding post-exposure prophylaxis (35.4%) and anti-HBs titer testing (18.9%) was low. A total of 31.2% reported having had a needle-stick injury, but less than half formally reported it. A significant positive correlation was found between knowledge, attitude, and practice scores ($p < 0.05$).**Conclusion:** While knowledge and attitudes toward Hepatitis B among medical students were satisfactory, actual preventive practices were inadequate. The gap between awareness and implementation underscores the need for institutional strategies such as mandatory vaccination, enhanced HBV education, and improved safety protocols.**Keywords:** Hepatitis B, KAP study, medical students, vaccination, needle-stick injury, public health, Udaipur, infection control.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection remains a pressing global health concern, responsible for significant morbidity and mortality. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that approximately 296 million people were living with chronic hepatitis B infection worldwide in 2019, with nearly 820,000 deaths annually attributed to cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), complications arising from untreated HBV infection [1]. Hepatitis B is a blood-borne virus transmitted through exposure to infected blood and bodily fluids, making healthcare professionals and medical students particularly vulnerable due to their frequent contact with patients, blood products,

and sharp instruments during their clinical training [2,3]. In India, HBV infection constitutes a substantial public health burden, with an intermediate endemicity level and a carrier rate of 2% to 8% among the general population [4]. Among healthcare workers, the risk is several times higher due to occupational exposure. Studies report that over 60% of medical students and interns in India are unaware of essential safety practices and remain unvaccinated despite having access to healthcare facilities [5,6]. Moreover, studies indicate that the risk of HBV infection following a percutaneous exposure to HBsAg-positive blood is as high as 30%, making preventive strategies such

as vaccination, awareness, and proper handling of needle-stick injuries critical [7]. Medical students, particularly during their clinical years, are at the forefront of patient interaction and often undertake procedures such as blood sampling, cannulation, and minor surgical interventions. A study from Chennai found that although 90% of students were aware of the infectious nature of HBV, only 35% had completed the three-dose vaccination schedule [8]. In another study conducted in Uttarakhand, only 54% of medical students were found to have good knowledge of HBV, and even fewer demonstrated appropriate attitudes and safe practices [9]. These knowledge-practice gaps are consistent across various parts of India and indicate a widespread disconnect between theoretical knowledge and real-world action [10].

Udaipur, located in southern Rajasthan, is home to several medical institutions where undergraduate medical students receive intensive training. However, no recent study has assessed their knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding Hepatitis B prevention and management. Considering their imminent entry into clinical practice, it is imperative to evaluate the preparedness of these future doctors in safeguarding themselves and their patients from HBV infection. Identifying gaps in knowledge and practices can assist in the formulation of targeted educational interventions, promotion of complete vaccination, and development of institutional policies on occupational exposure.

Therefore, this study aims to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practices of undergraduate medical students in Udaipur towards Hepatitis B infection. Understanding the current level of awareness and behavior will help design effective training and policy-level interventions to protect this high-risk group and prevent nosocomial transmission of HBV.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: This was a descriptive, institution-based cross-sectional study conducted among undergraduate medical students of a tertiary medical college in Udaipur, Rajasthan, during the period 1 August to 30 September 2024.

Study Population: The study population included undergraduate MBBS students (1st year to final year including interns) enrolled at the selected medical college. Students absent during data collection or unwilling to participate were excluded.

Sample Size: The sample size was calculated using the formula for cross-sectional studies:

$$n = Z^2 \times P \times (1-P) / d^2$$

Where:

- $Z = 1.96$ (95% confidence level)
- $p =$ expected proportion of good knowledge about Hepatitis B [taken as 55% from previous study in Uttarakhand (11)]
- $d =$ absolute precision (5%)

$$n = (1.96)^2 \times 55 \times 45 / 5^2 = 381$$

Assuming a 10% non-response rate, the final sample size was ~420 students.

Sampling Technique:

A stratified random sampling technique was adopted. MBBS students were stratified based on their academic year (1st, 2nd, 3rd, final year, and interns). From each stratum, participants were selected using proportionate random sampling to ensure adequate representation from all academic levels.

Study Tool and Data Collection: A pre-tested, semi-structured, self-administered questionnaire was used. It was designed based on previous validated KAP studies and modified to suit the local context. The questionnaire was divided into four sections:

Section I: Socio-demographic Data - Age, gender, year of study, vaccination status, history of needle-stick injury, and prior training on infection control.

Section II: Knowledge -

- 15 multiple-choice questions covering transmission routes, clinical features, prevention, vaccine schedule, and post-exposure prophylaxis.
- Each correct response awarded 1 point; incorrect or "don't know" responses scored 0.
- Total knowledge score range: 0–15.

Section III: Attitude -

- 10 statements rated on a 5-point Likert scale (Strongly agree to strongly disagree), assessing attitudes towards risk perception, responsibility, vaccination importance, and patient care.
- Positive attitudes scored higher.

Section IV: Practices -

- Questions regarding vaccination history (doses received), post-vaccine titer testing, needle-stick exposure management, use of gloves, and reporting behavior.
- Responses were both binary (yes/no) and frequency-based.

Scoring and Categorization -

- Knowledge: Scores $\geq 75\%$ considered good; $< 75\%$ considered poor.
- Attitude: Positive attitude defined as a mean score ≥ 4 out of 5.

- Practice: Good practice defined as completion of full 3-dose vaccination and appropriate exposure management behavior.

Data Collection Procedure: The questionnaire was distributed in person during lecture hours after obtaining informed consent. The purpose of the study was explained beforehand, and privacy was assured. Students were requested not to consult books or peers during the survey.

Data Entry and Analysis: Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 25. For descriptive statistics frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were calculated. For inferential statistics, Chi-square test to assess association between categorical variables, Independent t-test/ANOVA to compare mean KAP scores across different groups. Pearson correlation coefficient to assess correlation between

knowledge, attitude, and practice scores. Significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical Considerations:

- Informed written consent was obtained from each participant.
- Participation was voluntary, and anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout the study.
- Students could withdraw at any stage without any consequence.

Results

A total of 420 undergraduate medical students participated in the study. The mean age of the participants was 21.4 ± 1.8 years, with 57.6% (n=242) being females and 42.4% (n=178) males. Distribution of participants by academic year and gender shown in table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Participants by Academic Year and Gender (n = 420)

Academic Year	Male (n)	Female (n)	Total (n)	Percentage (%)
1st Year	36	50	86	20.5%
2nd Year	38	58	96	22.9%
3rd Year	39	60	99	23.6%
Final Year	36	43	79	18.8%
Interns	29	31	60	14.2%
Total	178	242	420	100%

Knowledge Regarding Hepatitis B Infection:

The knowledge score ranged from 3 to 15, with a mean of 10.8 ± 2.6 . Based on a cutoff of $\geq 75\%$ ($\geq 12/15$), 59.3% (n=249) of students had good knowledge, while 40.7% (n=171) had poor

knowledge. A statistically significant association was found between academic year and knowledge score ($p < 0.001$), with interns and final-year students scoring higher. Knowledge items and correct responses are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Knowledge Items and Correct Responses

Knowledge Item	Correct Responses (%) (n=420)
Hepatitis B is a viral infection affecting the liver	387 (92.1%)
Transmitted via blood and body fluids	372 (88.6%)
Vaccine schedule: 0, 1, and 6 months	333 (79.2%)
HBV more infectious than HIV	173 (41.2%)
Availability of post-exposure prophylaxis	149 (35.4%)
Knowledge of anti-HBs titer testing post-vaccination	79 (18.9%)

Attitude towards Hepatitis B Prevention: Attitude was assessed using a 5-point Likert scale. The mean attitude score was 4.2 ± 0.6 , with 71.2% (n=299) demonstrating a positive attitude (score ≥ 4). A moderate positive correlation was found between knowledge and attitude scores ($r = 0.44$, $p < 0.01$). Key attitudinal responses shown in table 3.

Table 3: Attitude Responses (Strongly Agree/Agree)

Statement	Agreement (%)
Medical students are at risk of Hepatitis B infection	376 (89.5%)
Vaccination should be mandatory for clinical exposure	343 (81.7%)
I am responsible for preventing HBV transmission	321 (76.4%)
Reporting needle-stick injuries is important	266 (63.3%)
I would feel ashamed if diagnosed with Hepatitis B	90 (21.4%)

Practices Related to Hepatitis B Prevention: Practice was evaluated based on vaccination history, exposure response, and infection control behaviors. Students with good knowledge had significantly better practices,

including higher vaccination rates and use of precautions ($p < 0.05$). Practice pattern among participants shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Practice Patterns among Participants

Practice Area	Frequency (%)
Fully vaccinated (3 doses completed)	230 (54.8%)
Only 1 or 2 doses received	90 (21.4%)
Unvaccinated	100 (23.8%)
Underwent anti-HBs titer testing	30 (7.1%)
Ever had a needle-stick injury	131 (31.2%)
Reported needle-stick injury	64 (48.7% of above)
Always use gloves during patient care	279 (66.4%)
Would seek care after HBV exposure	303 (72.1%)

Correlation between KAP Domains

Statistical analysis revealed positive and significant correlations among all three domains:

- Knowledge vs Attitude: $r = 0.44$, $p < 0.01$
- Knowledge vs Practice: $r = 0.36$, $p < 0.01$
- Attitude vs Practice: $r = 0.41$, $p < 0.01$

Discussion

This study assessed the knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding Hepatitis B infection among medical students in Udaipur, with the aim of identifying gaps and suggesting interventions for better prevention strategies.

Knowledge Regarding Hepatitis B

The overall knowledge score was satisfactory, with 59.3% of students demonstrating good knowledge. This aligns with findings from studies conducted in India and abroad, where the knowledge level ranged from 45% to 75% among medical students [12-14]. Most participants were aware that Hepatitis B is a viral disease affecting the liver and knew about major routes of transmission, including blood and body fluids. However, awareness regarding the increased infectivity of Hepatitis B compared to HIV was low, consistent with other studies in which this was an under-recognized fact [15-16]. Only 35.4% of participants were aware of post-exposure prophylaxis, and a mere 18.9% had knowledge of anti-HBs titer testing after vaccination. Similar knowledge gaps have been reported in other Indian studies, reflecting inadequate integration of Hepatitis B education into medical training [17-18].

Knowledge scores increased significantly with academic progression, highlighting the impact of clinical exposure on student awareness. This is consistent with findings from studies in Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu [19-20].

Attitude towards Hepatitis B Prevention

A positive attitude was seen in 71.2% of students, similar to findings in comparable cross-sectional studies [13,21]. Most students agreed that they are

at risk during clinical practice and supported mandatory vaccination prior to clinical postings. This proactive attitude can be harnessed through targeted vaccination drives and training. However, a notable proportion (21.5%) expressed apprehension regarding stigma if diagnosed with Hepatitis B. This finding underscores the continued presence of social stigma and misperceptions, despite being in a medical environment.

The study observed a moderate positive correlation between knowledge and attitude, suggesting that better understanding can improve perceptions toward prevention and responsibility.

Practices Related to Hepatitis B Prevention

While knowledge and attitude were generally favourable, actual practice was suboptimal. Only 54.8% of students were fully vaccinated, a figure lower than ideal considering their high-risk status. Other studies in Indian medical colleges have reported similar or slightly higher coverage rates, ranging from 50% to 70% [14,18,22].

Worryingly, only 7.1% had undergone anti-HBs titer testing after vaccination. Post-vaccination testing is essential for ensuring immunity, especially in high-risk groups like healthcare workers and students [23]. About 31.2% of students reported at least one needle-stick injury, yet less than half formally reported it. This trend is concerning and mirrors underreporting in similar studies [24]. Underutilization of reporting mechanisms could be due to fear, lack of knowledge, or administrative barriers.

Overall, a positive correlation was found between knowledge, attitude, and practice scores. This reaffirms the importance of educational interventions in influencing behavior. Students with better knowledge had significantly better vaccination coverage and infection control practices.

Conclusions

This cross-sectional study among medical students in Udaipur highlighted important gaps between

knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) related to Hepatitis B infection. While a majority of students demonstrated good knowledge and a positive attitude, actual preventive practices were inadequate. Only 54.8% were fully vaccinated, and just 7.1% had undergone anti-HBs titer testing. Despite awareness of risks, many students did not report needle-stick injuries, indicating underutilization of safety protocols.

A significant positive correlation was observed between knowledge, attitude, and practice scores, suggesting that improved awareness can lead to better preventive behavior. These findings underscore the need for comprehensive education on Hepatitis B early in the medical curriculum, along with mandatory vaccination and post-vaccination screening. Strengthening reporting systems and reducing stigma are also crucial.

Enhancing KAP among medical students is essential not only for their personal safety but also to prevent the spread of infection in healthcare settings and the wider community.

References

1. World Health Organization. Hepatitis B. [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2024 Jun 12]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/hepatitis-b>
2. Singhal V, Bora D, Singh S. Hepatitis B in health care workers: Indian scenario. *J Lab Physicians*. 2009; 1(2):41–8.
3. Sharma R, Rasania SK, Verma A, et al. Study of prevalence and response to needlestick injuries among health care workers in a tertiary care hospital in Delhi, India. *Indian J Community Med*. 2010; 35(1):74–7.
4. Batham A, Narula D, Toteja T, et al. Systematic review and meta-analysis of prevalence of hepatitis B in India. *Indian Pediatr*. 2007; 44(9):663–74.
5. Bharambe MS, Akarte SV, Kakrani VA. Knowledge, attitude and practice of universal work precautions with reference to HIV/AIDS among junior doctors and nurses. *Indian J Community Med*. 2008; 33(1):22–3.
6. Karani H, Patel M, Patel A. Knowledge, attitude and practice regarding hepatitis B infection among healthcare students. *Int J Med Sci Public Health*. 2016; 5(6):1153–7.
7. Beltrami EM, Williams IT, Shapiro CN, et al. Risk and management of blood-borne infections in health care workers. *Clin Microbiol Rev*. 2000; 13(3):385–407.
8. Jayakruthiga R, Kowsalya R, Suman S. A study on knowledge, attitude and practice of hepatitis B infection among medical students of Chennai. *Int J Community Med Public Health*. 2017; 4(9):3304–7.
9. Sharma A, Sharma SK, Singhal A, et al. Hepatitis B vaccination status and awareness among health care workers in a tertiary care hospital in Uttarakhand. *J Commun Dis*. 2016; 48(2):15–20.
10. Gupta V, Mishra S, Bansal R. Knowledge, attitude and practice regarding hepatitis B infection among medical and nursing students. *Int J Community Med Public Health*. 2019; 6(12):5250–5.
11. Chhabra D, Mishra S, Gawande K, Sharma A, Kishore S, Bhadoria AS. Knowledge, attitude, and practice study on hepatitis B among medical and nursing undergraduate students of an apex healthcare institute at Uttarakhand foothills: A descriptive analysis. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*. 2019 Jul 1; 8(7):2354-60.
12. Sharma R, Bhasin S. Hepatitis B: Knowledge and practices among medical students. *J Commun Dis*. 2010; 42(2):93–7.
13. Aggarwal V, Bansal R, Sharma V. Hepatitis B awareness and vaccination status among undergraduate medical students. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2014; 8(3):HC19–22.
14. Singhal V, Bora D, Singh S. Hepatitis B in health care workers: Indian scenario. *J Lab Physicians*. 2009; 1(2):41–8.
15. Abraham G, Shroff S, Murugesan A. Low awareness of HBV among medical students in South India. *Indian J Gastroenterol*. 2012; 31(3):127–9.
16. Mehta SP, Bansal R, Dhot PS. Awareness regarding hepatitis B and C infections among medical students. *Indian J Med Microbiol*. 2013; 31(3):227–9.
17. Sandeep G, Akash P, Rathi P. Awareness and practices regarding Hepatitis B among MBBS students in Maharashtra. *Int J Med Sci Public Health*. 2016; 5(9):1770–4.
18. Krishnappa S, Kumari M, Singh M. Hepatitis B vaccine compliance among healthcare students. *Asian J Med Sci*. 2018; 9(6):25–9.
19. Giri PA, Phalke DB. Knowledge and practices about hepatitis B among medical and nursing students. *Int J Health Allied Sci*. 2013; 2(1):41–3.
20. Subburaj P, Ganesan D, Thangaraj S. Hepatitis B vaccine compliance and knowledge among interns in Tamil Nadu. *Int J Community Med Public Health*. 2020; 7(2):456–60.
21. Dutta S, Misra R. Perception and practice of medical students about hepatitis B vaccination. *Indian J Public Health*. 2011; 55(1):20–3.
22. Singh A, Jain S, Kiran K. Hepatitis B awareness and vaccination status among healthcare workers in a tertiary care hospital. *J Infect Public Health*. 2016; 9(4):396–403.
23. WHO. Hepatitis B. World Health Organization Fact Sheet. 2023. Available from:

<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/hepatitis-b>

24. Askarian M, Malekmakan L. Needle-stick injuries among medical students. *Med Educ.* 2006; 40(2):160–3.